

LISA

LASER IONISATION AND SPECTROSCOPY OF ACTINIDES

ANNUAL NEWSLETTER

SEPTEMBER 2022

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NOTE FROM THE EDITORS

Laser Ionization and Spectroscopy of Actinides, LISA, is the name of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network (ITN) grant agreement no. 861198, kicked off 1 November 2019. This edition of the LISA annual newsletter offers a glimpse into the activities and accomplishments of the network in its second year and features work from our 15 early stage researchers (ESRs).

Our second newsletter captures some of the highlights of the year. Secondments across continents, large research collaborations, and training events hosted by LISA. The research topics span a diverse set of areas, but LISA brings these different disciplines together: the experimental, the theoretical, the on-line, the off-line. Learning together and apart, we build the connections that propel science forward another generation.

We hope you enjoy this newsletter, and encourage you to follow our activities on social media, where you'll find updates on upcoming trainings, events, and research.

NOTE FROM THE EDITORIAL BOARD

How can you start a network during the pandemic!? You just do, and LISA did it. The LISA recruitment event is the last trip that many supervisors were allowed to do in March 2019 before the lockdowns, and all of our ESRs have started their time in LISA during one phase of the COVID-19 pandemic or another.

In spite of the less-than-optimal conditions, the ESRs built up their momentum: from timid online coffee-hours¹ to break the monotonous teleworking days, to online training events, we thought we would never get out of this. However, it happened: the trainings became hybrid and then fully in person. We had conquered it all. Or so we thought.

And then we got struck again. All the planning for our Tenerife school in the winter of 2022 got pulled from under our feet, and with it, the chance to gather and exchange on our progress. There followed a lot of hesitation, delays, until we finally could start planning again, as fast as we could, to bring the community together in two weeks of celebration for the actinides in back-to-back LISA schools, organized September 2022 in Normandy.

As for progress, there is aplenty! LISA went through its periodic report to the European Commission and compiling the achievements by the ESRs was impressive. They have gone sometimes beyond our expectations, impressing all supervisors within the network, and certainly our Coordinator, Bruce. This newsletter is testament to their great capability and their hard work together. From novel technical developments, to breaking new grounds in the atom or the nucleus, and bringing all this to society, we have a lot to be proud of. They have a lot to be proud of.

I would say that we live through a golden era of LISA, but I should certainly stand corrected and say that we live in an actinide era! So, let it shine!!

Thomas Elias Cocolios, Training Officer and Bruce Marsh, Coordinator.

¹This hour has 45 minutes..

BENEFICIARIES

PARTNERS

YEAR IN REVIEW

Right in the thick of it would be a good way to describe the stage at which we find ourselves at the end of our second year. With the renewed ability to travel, collaborative experiments are running at full speed, conferences are buzzing, and the training is translating into skill and confidence. This year we welcomed new ESRs Asar Jaradat (CERN), Joseph Andrews (FSU Jena), Fedor Ivandikov (KU Leuven), and congratulate associate Steven Nothhelfer (GSI Darmstadt) on completing his PhD.

Back in September 2021, ESRs in WP3: Societal Applications attended the **Applied Nuclear Physics Conference** in Prague, Czech Republic. A diverse range of topics were presented, from medical applications in theragnostics and dosimetry, to materials analysis for nuclear reactors and archaeology. While ion beams were strongly represented in the conference, LISA brought lasers to the table, showing off its strong capabilities in added element selectivity.

Early October brought many ESRs, affiliates, and supervisors together to enjoy a final week of bright summer weather at the **Joliot-Curie International School** on the island of Saint Pierre d'Oléron off the west coast of France. The lectures were centered around the interplay between atomic electrons and the nucleus. Laser spectroscopy was at the forefront, with LISA-affiliated speakers lecturing on both theory and experiment on topics such as atomic structure calculations (Anastasia Borschevsky, Univ. of Groningen and Stephan Fritzsche, FSU, Jena), laser spectroscopy for nuclear moments and charge radii (Iain Moore and Ruben de Groote, JYU, Jyväskylä), and the Physics and Chemistry of heavy elements (Sebastian Raeder, GSI, Darmstadt).

These themes continued as Jyväskylä hosted **LISA Specialized Training 2: Advanced Techniques for the Production and Study of Actinides**. The cold dark north of Finland announced that summer was definitely over. Lectures were put into practice in the accelerator lab, training with ion trapping techniques, laser spectroscopy, materials-based analysis methods and electromagnetic recoil separators. It is one thing to attend atomic theory lectures, but another to see the facilities in which they are experimentally validated. Accelerator facilities form a large part of the LISA network, making comparisons between facilities vital for those in the field. Even so, for those not in day-to-day interaction with accelerators, the training provided a richer context in fundamental research.

*Left: Jessica Warbinek (GSI), Mia Au (CERN), and Miranda Nichols (Gothenburg) left to right at the Specialized Training 2 in Jyväskylä.
Right: Magdalena Kaja (JGU) and Anjali Ajayakumar (GANIL) left to right at the Applied Nuclear Physics Conference in Prague.*

Andrea Raggio (JYU) adjusting lasers at the LISA Training at JYU in Finland.

Winter saw the return of international turbulence. Travel restrictions resulted in the postponement of the already postponed LISA winter school further into the summer. The war in Ukraine brought an immediate cancellation to the LISA4Society Action field study in the Chernobyl Exclusion Zone, with an alternative sampling site planned for spring 2023.

Other events were still on, including the **Laser World of Photonics**, showcasing laser technology advancements in industry and applications in academic research. A fast-paced, two day workshop **EOS Molecular, Atomic, Nuclear and ASTrophysics research for heavy eLements studies—MANASLU** was hosted in Mons/Bergen Belgium.

The spring saw many collaborative efforts from the ISOLDE facility at CERN, with a running period starting in mid-March and many members of the LISA network coming to collaborate in the ongoing activities. ESRs contributed in initial setup beam time before the running period (Mia and Magdalena), joined experiments on the collinear resonance ionization spectroscopy of aluminum isotopes (Miranda, Julius) and silver (Miranda, Julius, Mitzi, Magdalena), as well as experiments on the production of radioactive molecular beams (Mia, Wiktorja) and in-source laser spectroscopy of actinium (Asar, Mia, Magdalena, Fedor) and polonium (Miranda, Asar, Jake).

The **LISA Summer Schools** will take place in September. Summer school 1, **From the Nucleons to the Stars**, focuses on the nucleus, its properties and applications, while also touching on soft skills like grant writing and project management. It is hosted by GANIL, and includes a tour of the accelerator technology complex surrounding GANIL. Summer school 2, **Structure of Complex Atoms**, goes further into light-matter interactions and computation, with a soft skill focus on ethics and career building in academia and industry.

Through the far-flung corners of the world, LISA continues to shine light on the heaviest atoms, finding ever more questions, complications, solutions, frustrations and discoveries. On we go!

Novel Techniques and Technologies for Actinide Research

Progress from Work Package 2

Mia Au

Research is enabled by the eventual results of stubborn perseverance on all sides of a challenge. From the production of actinide ion beams to the development of lasers for spectroscopy, researchers in WP2 work to push research capabilities further into the actinide region.

This year brought major milestones to the ISOLDE facility at CERN, where LISA ESRs Asar Jaradat and Mia Au work on extending the ISOL technique for the actinides. The PI-LIST (Perpendicularly-illuminated laser ion source and trap) [1] was successfully implemented at ISOLDE. The team demonstrated the capability of the technique to suppress surface-ionized background and push below the Doppler limit towards high-resolution in-source spectroscopy. In May,

the team ended an ambitious in-source spectroscopy program with the successful conclusion of the IS664 experiment on octupole deformation in actinium isotopes. The year saw two new actinide beams of atomic neptunium and plutonium successfully produced and identified, pushing isotope

yields at ISOLDE above the target nucleus. In another major online experiment, molecular extraction was successfully used to produce actinide molecules, opening new avenues for spectroscopy on radioactive molecular ions.

At the S³-Low-Energy Branch setup at SPIRAL2-GANIL, LISA ESR Anjali Ajayakumar works on developments for laser ionization spectroscopy of ions in a gas jet. This year, the GISELE laser laboratory was commissioned with erbium, delivering a proof-of-principle experiment using the new injection-locked, pulsed Ti:Sa laser system designed for S³-LEB. In a feature article about GANIL, Anjali details the importance of this upcoming facility.

The year has been a good one for the implementation of laser technologies, with ESRs Julius Wessolek and Mitzi Urquiza bringing laser developments directly to experiment. The IS660 experiment at the ISOLDE-CRIS setup used a 328 nm first excitation step for resonance ionization spectroscopy of silver isotopes and compared the performance of several laser configurations. Light from an injection-locked Ti:Sa system was frequency mixed with the 532 nm light of a Nd:YAG laser, providing narrowband light for the high-resolution spectroscopy. For direct comparison, the C-WAVE OPO laser travelled from Hübner Photonics to CERN. In our research highlights, Julius and Mitzi describe the comparison of the two laser techniques used to generate the specific laser light needed for high-resolution spectroscopy experiments.

From producing, extracting and ionizing beams of actinide isotopes to commissioning new facilities to developing the laser light required to perform the experiments, the work from the ESRs in WP2 sets the rest of the network up with tools and techniques to study the actinides.

A nuclear chart of actinide isotopes produced by simulating 1.4 GeV protons interacting with a uranium carbide (UC_x) target material, with the number of nuclei produced per micro-Coulomb of protons indicated along with the half-life. (isoyields2.web.cern.ch)

Hübner Photonics C-WAVE system

Societal Applications

Progress from Work Package 3

Darcy van Eerten

Grating-tuned Ti:Sa laser at IRS.

We know a lot of things are possible, but are they reliable? Standardized? Adaptable? Fool proof? *Rugged?* These are important questions when developing technology, even when you spend half your time worrying about the influence of hyperfine interactions on your measurement. Juggling between the quantum mechanics of transition probabilities and tweaking mirrors for laser alignment, only to end up with too little useful yield. Efficiency is everything, but that goal becomes fuzzier when balancing sacrificed signal for increased selectivity.

Jake Johnson (KU Leuven), who details his work further in the feature article in this newsletter, must decide on the most efficient way to collect ^{225}Ac produced at ISOLDE. Removing it from the target itself is the first challenge, overcome by heating the sample to very high temperatures. Laser ionization then separates the Ac from the other nuclides, leading to a promising path for medically relevant isotope production. The next step will be to improve the efficiency further, and extend the question to ^{225}Ra , an isobar that could be a useful source of Ac.

Questions around isobars are also being asked in Hannover by Darcy van Eerten (IRS-LUH). Organic chemistry spares no souls, overwhelming mass spectrometry of environmental samples, and obscuring signals coming from trace isotopes present in nuclear fuel. With the implementation of multi-element switching made possible by the grating-tuned Ti:Sa lasers, trace elements can be analysed at microscopic levels one after the other.

Darcy and Jake's secondments, in this second year, came at a critical point to compare techniques in different laboratories, and see where strengths can be transferred, and weaknesses overcome. Jake at CERN-ISOLDE and at TRIUMF in Vancouver, Canada, got a hands-on look at radio-isotope production. Darcy went to LLNL in Livermore, USA, to reanalyse samples from Chernobyl and compare results. These rich and fruitful exchanges highlighted the similarities, differences, and challenges faced in these techniques, key to maximising their efficiency.

Enhanced Understanding of Actinide Structure

Progress from Work Package 4

Mia Au

The LARISSA group at JGU Mainz uses Ti:Sapphire lasers specially developed for RIMS applications
<https://www.larissa.physik.uni-mainz.de/introduction/>

Investigations into atomic structure have been ongoing within Work Package 4, where researchers use experiment and theory to tackle the complicated configurations of electrons present in the actinide elements.

In the LARISSA lab at Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz, LISA ESR Magdalena Kaja has been busy at the RISIKO mass separator facility, developing new ionization schemes for the challenging element neptunium.

Charged with an opposite task, ESR Miranda Nichols has brought negative ions to the CRIS experiment at CERN-ISOLDE as part of her secondment. A neutral particle detector was developed in Gothenburg, Sweden, allowing for observation of neutrals from the sodium vapor charge exchange cell at the CRIS beamline. This year, the successful implementation of the neutral particle detector enabled investigations of the charge exchange behavior of ^{238}U , ^{211}Po , and ^{219}Fr , characterizing the optimum conditions for the formation of negative ions. A model is now being worked on to fit this data to investigate if any information on the atomic structure can be extracted, with a proposal set to measure the electron affinity in Po, Fr, Np, and U, as only U has been measured so far.

Neutral particle detector at CRIS

Hand in hand with experiment, theoretical calculations give meaning to experimental observables and allow researchers to extract important information from results. At Rijksuniversiteit Groningen, ESR Raphaël Crosa-Rossa has calculated the electron affinity of tellurium and polonium using the relativistic single reference coupled cluster approach. Comparing with existing experimental results and extending the calculations both lighter to the element selenium and heavier to the element livermorium, the CCSD(T) approach shows dependence of electron correlations in these atomic properties.

At Friedrich Schiller-Universität Jena, ESR Joseph Andrews investigates hyperfine constants of heavy atoms using multi-configurational Dirac Hartree Fock methods. The development of dedicated codes for atomic structure calculations is ongoing.

The ESRs of WP4 use the symbiosis of theoretical and experimental information to build our knowledge of actinide atomic structure.

Exploring the Limits of Nuclear Existence

Progress from Work Package 5
Darcy van Eerten

There are many secrets remaining in the nuclide chart. From the far edges to the deep valley in the centre, we find all sorts of short-lived states, the origin and purpose of which can be hinted at in theoretical models, but require experimental observation to be validated. These exotic states need to be both produced and analysed in the most optimized conditions to squeeze out these rare properties.

Hidden in the centre of the nuclide chart we find so-called isomers, an intermediate state populated by decay before it relaxes into a stable state. One of the lowest known isomers is ^{235m}U , with a half-life of 26 minutes. To analyse such states, sources of ^{239}Pu and ^{240}Pu have to be produced as recoil ion sources, one to study ^{235}U , and another to comparatively study ^{236}U . Lauren Reed (JGU Mainz) has been developing these sources, which display the wide variety of striking colors seen in the below image.

Just when you think you know how actinides behave, they throw you a curveball. At the IGISOL facility in Jyväskylä, Andrea Raggio (JYU) is observing them with a gas-cell-based ion source. While resonant laser ionization is both selective and highly efficient in vacuum, this efficiency is reduced when in a gas-cell environment. Recently published in *Atoms* (see research highlights), collision-induced phenomena of plutonium in helium gas are reported, causing de-excitation which competes with the resonance ionization process of the lasers.

The gas-cell method is being worked on by Fedor Ivandikov (KU Leuven), where the specialized De Laval gas nozzle is being implemented in experiments across Europe. Already mentioned is IGISOL, but also experiments in GANIL (see feature article).

Even rarer isotopes suffer from exceedingly short lifetimes, like ^{251}No with a half-life of 0.8 seconds. Jessica Warbinek (GSI, see research collabs, research highlights), is hard at work increasing the capabilities of the RADRIS method, including the nuclides that are accessible, and the overall efficiency of the method. With it, the atomic levels of the heaviest actinide lawrencium can be investigated, ever pushing toward the edges of our nuclear understanding.

Plutonium recoil ion sources with an optimized molecular plating method, developed at JGU Mainz. Top: photographs of samples. Bottom: radiographic images of samples.

Particle Accelerators are the Modern Philosopher's Stone

Jake Johnson

Four classical elements as classified by Aristotle: air, water, earth, and fire.

Since antiquity, there has been a fascination with the notion that one material can be transmuted into another. Work towards accomplishing such a quest first began during the so-called 'golden age' of Arabic science in the 8th-13th centuries. In ancient Greece in the previous millennium, Aristotle had already noted that the four classical elements could be decomposed into a combination of the two qualities of humidity and temperature.

Arabic scholars then reasoned that by altering one of the qualities of the classical elements, materials can be transmuted [1]. They believed that *al iksir* was needed to perform such a transformation. This theorized soft reddish substance came to be known as the philosopher's stone and could 'turn common metals to gold'. Some even believed it could prolong life indefinitely [2]. The Arabs never found it. Yet through the ages, the quest for transmutation of common metal into gold went on, and did so in earnest.

The Arabic *Al-kimiya* became the alchemy of the renaissance, and alchemy became chemistry. The elements of antiquity became the "atomic" elements, that are now understood to be fundamental. Further study affirmed that although chemical compounds can be created through the means of chemical reactions – the atoms– the fundamental chemical units, stay as they are. If we start with a number, N, of atoms of a certain type, this number will not change no matter how they react chemically. Chemistry, even in the modern age, cannot fundamentally transmute one material into another.

The quest seemed set for failure. That is, until 1919. Ernest Rutherford had just returned from the war to his barren lab. With scant material, there was nothing to do but fire accelerated helium nuclei into nitrogen gas. Strangely enough, 'recoiling hydrogen atoms' – or protons - were observed in this process. But where did these protons come from if the only materials involved were nitrogen and helium? Takeo Shimizu and Patrick Blackett later took thousands of photographs of these reaction tracks in the newly developed cloud chamber. Their analysis confirmed Rutherford's belief [3]. The nitrogen-14 of the air had been transformed into oxygen-17. The first anthropogenic nuclear reaction, $^{14}\text{N}({}^4\text{He},{}^1\text{H})^{17}\text{O}$, had been observed. With it, the first real footprint had been planted in the alchemists' quest for transmutation of metal into gold. The answer, it would seem, lies not with the atom, but with the nucleus, the true identity of atoms. This is what must be changed should one material be transmuted to another.

Rutherford had found the two key ingredients for transmutation; the *prima materia* for the philosopher's stone: target nuclei and accelerated particles. Now, 100 years later, thousands of particle accelerators - transmutation machines - have been built around the

Left: The many nuclei produced by high energy (1.4 GeV) protons impacting uranium.

Right: How one element is selectively ionized from all those produced in the target.

globe [4]. During this time, scientists have almost routinely turned relatively common metals into gold, though often as a by-product of other activities.

Let's say accelerated protons at 92% of the speed of light are fired into uranium metal. A proton at this energy overcomes the repulsive electrostatic force of uranium's 92-proton nucleus and penetrates into it, sputtering fragments of nucleons as it does so. The result is the creation of one of hundreds of different isotopes, of many different elements. Some of these are gold. For a target with around 2×10^{23} atoms of uranium, one can produce $\sim 1 \times 10^8$ atoms of gold for every 6.25×10^{12} protons fired [5]. This corresponds to 100 million atoms of gold made per second! This sounds like an awful lot, but just 1 g of gold has approximately 3×10^{21} atoms. The proton synchrotron booster at CERN would therefore need to run for 10 million years to make just 1 g of gold from uranium. Before we even make 10% of this, the world's entire fossil fuel stock would be completely depleted from accelerator operation alone† – not to mention the amount of coffee needed to sustain the operators [6,7]. So, while transmutation of common metals to gold has been accomplished – its interest remains purely scientific .

On the other hand, gold is not the only substance that is made through nuclear reactions at facilities like ISOLDE at CERN. Just as the philosopher's stone, or *al-iksir* was purported to have life-prolonging properties, so with particle accelerators and metal targets one can actually make isotopes that have real medicinal value. These isotopes do not prolong life indefinitely, but are used for the treatment of some distributed cancers. Whereas gold requires macroscopic quantities for any 'meaningful' purpose, a typical dose of these medical isotopes comes in quantities of only 0.1 pico-grams. This corresponds to approximately a few hours of accelerator operation, or many doses over the period of a day.

The production of these medical isotopes, in fact, relies completely on transmutation of other materials. This is because these isotopes do not exist on Earth because they themselves transmute! A number, N, of radioactive (or unstable) atoms does not stay at N, like in chemical processes. Typically for medical isotopes, N halves every few days or so, though radioactive decay – the natural transmutation process. Oddly enough, it is this feature that makes isotopes useful at all for medical purposes. Whenever the nucleus of one of these atoms decays, ionizing radiation is released. This can have huge therapeutic value if the radio-isotopes are delivered to the right place in the body. This practice is known as targeted radionuclide therapy.

A sub branch of this, targeted alpha therapy, has shown great promise for the treatment of myeloma, leukemia and metastatic prostate cancer, amongst others [8]. The 'alpha' refers to the alpha decay of the medical isotope. An alpha particle, a cluster of two protons and two neutrons, is like a cannon ball shot from a cannon. It is emitted with such high energy that it simply pops off the electrons from the chemical bonds of any matter it traverses, before rapidly coming to a stop, exhausted. If the matter were say, cancer cells, then the alpha particle would pummel through DNA, mostly causing irreparable damage and stopping cell reproduction. This would be dangerous for healthy cells too, were it not for the fact that the alpha particle comes to a stop in about the width of a human hair, or the diameter of just a few cells. In fact, right now, radio-oncologists can selectively deliver atoms with alpha emitting nuclei to cancer cells.

The alpha-emitter-carrying targeting molecule is injected into the body, where it circulates until it reaches an ugly cancer cell, whose surface is festooned and riddled with gangly proteins. The target molecule recognizes and latches on to one of these, while sparing the cleaner surface of healthy cells that have none, or very few of these targeted proteins. If the nucleus decays here, then the energy of the alpha particles is all dissipated in the cancer cells, offering powerful yet targeted treatment.

What's more, is that radiation damage to just a few clusters of cancer cells actually causes the targeted cells to go into distress, signaling to immune cells to sample the specific proteins on the targeted cell surfaces. The immune system then learns to recognize the malignant nature of these proteins, and activates tumor killing T-cells that target these specific proteins . The T-cells appropriately step in to take care of this type of malignant cell, wherever they are in the body. Though not yet fully understood, this process is known as the abscopal effect [9], and means some cancer cells are attacked without even seeing

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Mass selection of the ion beam. There can still be contaminants from neighbouring masses due to tails from the distribution of positions of the different mass ions.

TAT under the microscope. How the radiation damage is selectively localized.

What a radio-labelled ^{225}Ac pharmaceutical might look like.

An idealized view of where activity is distributed after the patient is injected.

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a single alpha particle themselves.

We are currently at a stage where we can produce and provide these 0.1 pico-gram quantities of alpha emitters to clinical researchers. They can then study therapeutic mechanisms associated with alpha emitters such as the abscopal effect, and also use them to actually treat patients in a number of ongoing clinical trials. Therein lies one of the challenges, it's hard to get enough to carry these trials through. These medical alpha-emitting isotopes are almost all actinides (or near-actinides) and thus rather difficult to study, and very difficult to produce in bulk and on-demand in clinically relevant amounts. This is where the mainstays of the LISA network come in. Radio-active ion beam facilities, lasers, mass separators, these tools are essential for some production techniques of these cancer-treating heavy medical isotopes, specifically actinium-225 (^{225}Ac): the work-horse of targeted alpha therapy research.

As mentioned earlier, isotopes like ^{225}Ac are produced in metal targets by transmutation reactions. Research in the LISA network is currently ongoing to decide on the most efficient way to collect ^{225}Ac from the targets, while ensuring that as few as possible of the hundreds of other isotopes co-produced in the target are collected along with it. The method that we pursue for this is called resonant laser ionization and mass separation. An overview is shown in images one to three. The lasers select the element based on their unique electronic energy levels, and the mass separator selects which isotope of the element we collect. Some heavier or lighter impurities come from tails of imperfect mass-separation. Other impurities come from surface ionization of isotopes of different elements with the same mass. ^{225}Ac is mostly lost along the way by sticking in the target, and through not being ionized. So far, we have determined that in ideal conditions, around 13% of whatever ^{225}Ac is in the target, we can collect. The major bottleneck is the laser ionization efficiency rather than stickiness. We have also determined that the target must be heated to a high temperature of around 2250 °C to 'sweat out' the ^{225}Ac if it is made in an environment supplied with oxygen atoms (this is because the atoms of ^{225}Ac readily bind with those of oxygen to form a stable ceramic-like substance) [10]. Finally, we have even measured the trace amount of a major contaminant* ^{227}Ac to be present in a collected sample. There is less than 1 decay of ^{227}Ac occurring for every million ^{225}Ac decays within our collected sample [11]. This means that in the future, we will need to focus on the efficiency of our method rather than spend time caring about the already very high purity.

In the future, our experiments will examine other alternative means of collecting the ^{225}Ac from targets. For example, could we change the chemical environment of the target to make ^{225}Ac form a more volatile compound, and make it easier to come out of the target at lower temperatures? How would we then best ionize such a molecule? How would the efficiency compare to what we have already measured? There is also the approach of collecting radium-225 (^{225}Ra), an isotope that naturally decays to ^{225}Ac , that can be harvested, or 'milked' every 18 days or so. What if we first collect ^{225}Ra using laser ionization and mass separation, then collect ^{225}Ac ? Is this more efficient? These many open questions in the production of ^{225}Ac are there to be answered. The efficiency of this new philosopher's stone can be improved. The LISA network will certainly be contributing to this in the next couple of years and beyond.

Grand Ambitions the Story of GANIL

Anjali Ajayakumar

Tucked away in an unassuming field, in what might otherwise be an unassuming business park in northern France, lies GANIL: *le Grand Accélérateur National d'Ions Lourds*, the large national heavy ion accelerator. It is large, and has grand ambitions to match. Progress in nuclear physics has, naturally, accelerated quickly over the last decade, with the construction and imminent completion of multiple facilities: ISOLDE at CERN, FAIR in Darmstadt (both involving LISA network members), as well as other projects beyond Europe. As the host of the LISA summer

school, it is worth taking some time to examine where GANIL lies in this accelerator ecosystem, and what exciting research we'll be hearing about for decades to come.

Fundamentally, accelerators boost charged particles, be that electrons, protons, or ions. The charged particles can themselves be studied, or directed into some sort of target. That target may be used to produce new material, or the behavior of the target itself may be investigated. It is often a combination of these: establish what needs to be accelerated, at what energy, and how that behaves, develop a target and predict how it will behave under the accelerated beam, collect and analyse everything that comes out. Different accelerators have different strengths, and answer different scientific questions. They play a role in subatomic research looking at the building blocks of the universe, the creation of short-lived isotopes used for medicine, and understanding the structure of complex materials, just to name a few.

Accelerator based isotope production

Ranging from the first CRT (cathode ray tube) televisions to the CT scans suffered in airport security lines, accelerator-based systems are widespread and ubiquitous in surprising ways. In RIB (radioactive ion beam) facilities, accelerators are used to drive the production of radioactive isotopes. The ISOLDE (Isotope Separator On-Line Device) facility at CERN pioneered the method using accelerated protons from CERN's accelerator complex to generate nuclear reaction products in target materials. Other facilities worldwide such as TRIUMF (Vancouver, Canada), IGISOL (Jyväskylä, Finland), GSI (Darmstadt, Germany), RIBF (Tokyo, Japan), FRIB (East Lansing, Michigan), and upcoming projects SPES (Legnaro, Italy), ISOL at MYRHHA (Mol, Belgium), and FAIR (Darmstadt, Germany) use their own accelerators and a variety of target materials to generate different catalogues of radioactive isotopes. GANIL and its new projects will play an important role in the worldwide landscape of accelerator-produced isotopes.

GANIL Today

GANIL is a heavy ion accelerator with five cyclotrons. It provides a range of ion beam energies that can deliver beams for several experiments at the same time. The ions are produced by an ECR (electron cyclotron resonance) ion source and injected into the cyclotron HF (high frequency) electric field, which increases the speed and energy of the ion, the trajectory of which is controlled by a magnetic field. The accelerated ions then collide with their target, after which the spectrometers with their electromagnetic elements separate the resulting fragments according to their mass and charge.

GANIL Tomorrow

How do you guarantee you win a lottery where the chances are one in a billion? Buy a billion tickets, and then some more. In essence, accelerators are needed for low-cross section experiments to a) ensure these very rare reactions occur and b) selectively separate the particles of interest without interference.

Currently under construction is the SPIRAL 2 LINAC facility, a linear accelerator that can provide beam intensities up to 14.5 MeV for heavy ions and also lighter nuclei. This accelerator will specialize in producing very heavy elements, particularly highly unstable neutron-deficient nuclei close to the proton dripline with lifetimes as low as 40 ms. To isolate these rare nuclei, the beams will feed into the S^3 (Super Separator Spectrometer), which can efficiently separate the ions of interest. S^3 -LEB will be the experimental room with the gas-cell based setup which will be at the focal plane of S^3 .

S^3 -LEB will allow the study of nuclei produced in very low cross section to 1 pps with high selectivity and high resolution in the order of 100s of MHz. That high efficiency is achieved by a narrowband laser system for selective ionization. It could also be coupled to other setups for mass measurement or decay spectroscopic studies apart from laser spectroscopy. These studies can give insights on the ground state and isomeric state properties, nuclear shape and size of elements in the nuclear chart that are currently not available in term of production cross section and lifetime.

The off-line commissioning work of the S^3 -LEB is currently in progress (see research highlights). Along with other facilities at the facility, such as the neutron source, the medical isotope and DESIR facilities, it is an exciting place right now, and in the future.

RESEARCH HIGHLIGHTS

Cover page of *Atoms* Volume 10 Issue 2

Research Highlighted:

Atoms (2022), **10** (2):

- [1] Warbinek et al., *Advancing Radiation-Detected Resonance Ionization towards Heavier Elements and More Exotic Nuclides*
- [2] Raggio et al., *Observation of Collisional De-Excitation Phenomena in Plutonium*.
- [3] Jekabs, Ajayakumar et al., *First Offline Results from the S3 Low-Energy Branch*.
- [4] Munzberg, Block, Claessens et al., *Resolution Characterizations of JetRIS in Mainz Using ^{164}Dy*
- [5] Weber, Dullman et al., *Probing the Atomic Structure of Californium by Resonance Ionization Spectroscopy*

RIMS:

- [6] Savina et al. (2021), *Photoionization and Photo-Induced Processes in Mass Spectrometry: Fundamentals and Applications* (eds R. Zimmermann and L. Hanley), **ch. 6**, 215-244.
- [7] Bosco et al. (2021), *Sci. Adv.*, **7**, eabj1175.
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- [10] Mandel et al. (2022), *J. of Hazard. Mater.*, **423**, 127143
- [11] Trappitsch et al. (2021), *84th Annual Meeting of the Meteoritical Society*, LPI Contribution No. 2609, id.6239

Atoms 2022: New Developments in the Production and Research of Actinide Elements

The virtual workshop *Atomic Structure of Actinides and Related Topics* was organized by Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz, the Helmholtz Institute Mainz, and the GSI Helmholtz Centre for Heavy Ion Research, Darmstadt, Germany. A number of LISA network members are featured, and the proceedings are found in *Atoms* 2022 in the Special Issue **Atomic Structure of the Heaviest Elements**, edited by Mustapha Laatiaoui and Sebastian Raeder.

The topics are diverse, but focus on the techniques used to understand atomic and nuclear structure. Jessica Warbinek writes on the RADRIS method, used to study nobelium, but is also a new movable double-detector setup, enabling the first laser spectroscopy measurements of the long-lived isotope ^{254}Fm [1]. Andrea Raggio describes how actinide beams are produced with gas-cell based accelerator facilities for plutonium [2]. Jekabs Romans, and Anjali Ajayakumar report on the offline commissioning of the GISELE lab using erbium [3]. Danny Munzberg, Michael Block, Arno Claessens et al. detail the resolution characterizations of JetRIS at Mainz, using ^{164}Dy [4].

Further studies are reported on the spectroscopy of heavy elements. The atomic structure of californium was investigated via laser spectroscopy by Felix Weber, Christoph Dullmann et al. [5].

Resonance Ionization Mass Spectrometry (RIMS)

It has been a great year for publishing in resonance ionization mass spectrometry (RIMS), marked by a devoted chapter in the recently published reference book on photoionization and photo-induced processes in mass spectrometry [6]. Five papers are highlighted here showcasing the use of tunable Ti:Sa lasers to do ultra-trace analysis and imaging of heavy elements in solid microscopic samples.

Three papers measured the isotope ratios in actinides, used as a tool in nuclear forensics investigations to determine the origin of a sample. Two papers from Hannover look at hot particles from Chernobyl, where one focusses on imaging the ultra-trace isotopes ^{238}Pu and $^{242\text{m}}\text{Am}$ with three lasers on one particle [7], and the other on the versatility of sequential multi-actinide analysis with two lasers on many particles [8]. Over in Livermore, the multi-element approach is achieved simultaneously by using six lasers, demonstrated in microscopic spent nuclear fuel samples [9].

Besides the actinides, exciting work has shown how trace amounts of Tc is taken up and distributed in plant cells, and informs how radionuclides behave in organic matter [10]. Further afield, further than our solar system even, RIMS has also been used to analyse presolar grains (aka stardust), looking at isotope ratios in elements like Ti and Mo to study s-process nucleosynthesis [11]. As RIMS is further developed, we will see it used to answer fundamental questions when investigating heavy elements: Where did it come from and how was it made?

RESEARCH COLLABS

Implementation of the PI-LIST at ISOLDE

Reinhard Heinke, Asar Jaradat, Mia Au, Magdalena Kaja

The PI-LIST (Perpendicularly Illuminated Laser Ion Source Trap) is an ion source designed for laser spectroscopy. The LIST structure features a mini radio-frequency (RF) quadrupole ion trap, providing radial confinement for a field-free ionization region. A separate hot atomization region—where nonselective ionization creates contamination—combined with a clean interaction region for element-selective laser ionization strongly enhances ion beam purity by orders of magnitude [2,3]. The addition of perpendicular laser illumination reduces effective Doppler broadening in the effusing hot vapor, enhancing spectral resolution [4].

Though the PI-LIST technique has a very successful history of offline implementation at the Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz [1], it had to overcome many hurdles to earn its new place at the radioactive ion beam (RIB) facility ISOLDE. RIB facilities come with the challenge of radioactivity, which must be designed into the implementation of any new technical development. Electrical services have to be transported into inaccessible zones, and all connections must be made remotely. Despite these challenges, the PI-LIST team overcame setbacks to conduct successful coupling tests. Starting in early March 2022—and continuing in April—two dedicated beam times focused on systematically characterizing the LIST performance on species of interest indium, ytterbium, tin, barium, and tellurium, as well as background suppression in regions of high experimental interest. All the prep work paid off in the ambitious and collaborative experiment IS664: Investigation of octupole deformation in neutron-rich actinium using high-resolution in-source laser spectroscopy. In May 2022, the team used the PI-LIST at ISOLDE to conduct the first high-resolution in-source spectroscopy of actinium, the first of the actinide series. The ISOLDE Decay Station (IDS) experiment joined in with decay spectroscopy, and ISOLDE's CRIS experiment contributed laser light, sending narrowband cw light from the CRIS laser lab to the RILIS laser lab to seed an injection-locked ring cavity Ti:Sa laser for high-resolution spectroscopy. The successful implementation of the PI-LIST at ISOLDE pushes the capability of in-source laser spectroscopy below previous resolution limits and enables the measurement of nuclear physics observables—a major step for laser spectroscopy and nuclear physics.

Laser developments for high resolution spectroscopy

Mitzi Urquiza, Julius Wessolek

The CRIS experiment at CERN ISOLDE was supported with the development of pulsed 328 nm laser light for the spectroscopy of exotic silver isotopes. Mitzi and her research team seeded a Pulsed Dye Amplifier (PDA) with the Hübner Photonics C-WAVE GTR tunable OPO system, at 656 nm single mode. With subsequent second harmonic generation (SHG), 328 nm light was generated and the wavelength could be continuously tuned to resolve the Hyperfine Structure (HFS) of the silver isotopes using the AbsoluteLambda option to the OPO system.

The performance of the OPO seeding a PDA was benchmarked against a fully solid state system. Developed by Julius with the help of the CRIS and RILIS teams at ISOLDE, in this system, 328 nm light was created by sum frequency generation of the light from an injection-locked pulsed Ti:Sa and a pulsed single mode 532 nm laser. Scanning the wavelength was achieved by scanning the cw seed laser of the injection-locked Ti:Sa.

Both schemes of generating light of the required wavelength have been highly successful and show the potential of both continuous wave OPO and sum frequency generation of narrowband pulsed light for high-resolution spectroscopy of actinides.

Top: simulation of standard in-source spectroscopy resolution (grey) compared against experimental PI-LIST data (black) and experimental fit (red) of ^{165}Ho , published in [1], highlighting the impact of improved resolution on extraction of meaningful observables.

References

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A 3D model of the LIST operating in PI mode, published in [1], showing the effusing atom cone (orange), the overlapping laser light (red) and the perpendicular spectroscopy laser (blue).

Mitzi Urquiza and Volker Sonnenschein (HÜBNER Photonics) setting up the widely tunable OPO system C-WAVE GTR at CERN.

Beta-delayed fission of neutron-rich Ac isotopes

Silvia Barra

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Schematic representation of the β DF process [1].

ASET connected to the beam line, with the HPGe detectors around it.

Installing the ladder system of detectors

Tired but satisfied experimenters. From left: Fedor Ivandikov (ESR 7), Silvia Barra (associate), Michael Heines and Viktor Van den Bergh (KU Leuven).

The distribution of elements that make up the universe is an ongoing scientific question. Establishing the probability of different modes of nucleosynthesis, the creation of nuclides, helps to answer it. Beta-delayed fission (β DF) is a decay mode by which a nucleus first undergoes β decay and then fissions from the excited state it populated. Besides its relevance in understanding nuclear structure and low-energy fission, this process may have a strong impact on the decay of heavy elements at the end of the r -process, altering the balance between the abundance of mid-heavy and heavy elements. β DF has only partially been studied experimentally, lacking especially in the neutron-rich side of the nuclide chart relevant to nucleosynthesis.

A first measurement was done at ISOLDE (CERN) where radioactive ion beams of $^{230, 232, 234}\text{Ra}$ were implanted and decayed into $^{230, 232, 234}\text{Ac}$ to observe the β DF. To estimate the number of implanted isotopes, HPGe detectors are used to detect γ rays (see figure 4). For ^{230}Ac , a β DF probability of $1.19(40) \times 10^{-9}$ was already reported in literature [1], and was chosen as starting point for this first measurement as a test for the experimental setup. Previously, ^{230}Ac was obtained from the decay of ^{230}Ra that was chemically separated from the other products of the multi-nucleon transfer reaction on a ThO_2 powder target. Mica foils, used as fission track detectors, were attached to the ^{230}Ra sample for 10 hours and for 20 different runs. In total only two tracks were identified as fission fragments coming from ^{230}Ac , and its β DF probability was tentatively reported to be on the order of 10^{-9} .

With such β DF probability and a production rate of about 10^6 pps for ^{230}Ra , a fission fragment rate of about 100 FF/shift was expected. However, no fission fragment was observed from the implanted isotopes. To be sure that this 'blindness' wasn't coming from the experimental setup, it was successfully tested with ^{202}Fr , a reference isotope for which the expected rate of β -delayed fission fragments was known. From the γ spectra, the amount of Ac decays was determined, and this allowed a preliminary estimation of a new upper limit for the β DF probability of about 10^{-10} for both ^{230}Ac and ^{232}Ac .

Before starting this experiment, some theoretical calculations were done using TALYS that combined the β -strength function of the mother with the fission barrier of the daughter to obtain the final probability. The results weren't very promising, especially for ^{230}Ac , probably because it was too low to be considered significant.

The upper limits estimated experimentally for ^{230}Ac and ^{232}Ac are still far away from the ones calculated with TALYS, but the fact that no fission fragment was seen for any of them may suggest that the β DF probability is even lower than the estimated value of 10^{-10} .

Laser spectroscopy of the heaviest elements at GSI

Jessica Warbinek-ESR 10, Andrea Raggio-ESR 4, Magdalena Kaja-ESR 5, Fedor Ivandikov-ESR 7

The study of the heaviest actinides recently gained much attention in the fields of atomic and nuclear physics and is a large endeavor also tackled in the framework of LISA. In these heavy elements the strong force and the Coulomb force are of similar strength and their stability is governed by shell effects. However, experimental information on the elements beyond fermium ($Z = 100$) is scarce as they can only be produced at on-line accelerator facilities and they need to be studied immediately after their production due to their short half-lives. Therefore, experimental techniques used to explore these exotic elements need to be highly selective and efficient at the same time, to allow experiments with atom-at-a-time quantities of the isotopes of interest [1].

Not too long ago, the Radiation Detected Resonance Ionization Spectroscopy method (RADRIS) [2, 3] allowed the first laser spectroscopy study on the second heaviest actinide, nobelium ($Z = 102$), at the GSI in Darmstadt [4]. This first observation of atomic levels in nobelium paved the way for the study of a chain of nobelium isotopes [5], to infer the first ionization potential of nobelium [6], as well as investigations of other heavy actinide elements. More recently, the development of the JetRIS apparatus for laser spectroscopy in a gas-jet yielded new possibilities to determine nuclear ground state properties of the heaviest actinides with higher precision [7, 8].

In the recent FAIR phase-0 beamtime campaign at the GSI in Darmstadt, Germany, from March to June 2022 at the SHIP separator, different international research groups, ESRs, and affiliates within LISA joined forces to perform laser spectroscopy studies of the heaviest actinides. In this extensive campaign, the RADRIS and JetRIS setups were employed for different approaches to study nuclei beyond $Z=98$.

The well-established RADRIS method was applied for the search for atomic levels in the heaviest actinide element, lawrencium ($Z = 103$). To date, only theoretical predictions exist allowing to guide experimental investigations. However, the theoretical uncertainties result in a large scan range that has not been fully covered yet, and no atomic level was experimentally observed so far. Besides the search for atomic levels and in addition to studying further fermium and californium ($Z = 98$) isotopes, a first laser spectroscopy study on the short-lived isotope ^{251}No ($t_{1/2} = 0.8$ s) was performed by the international team of researchers.

The new gas-jet apparatus JetRIS was successfully commissioned in an on-line experiment: for the first time, in-gas-jet laser spectroscopy of ^{254}No was achieved. In the future, this apparatus will help to increase the resolution for laser spectroscopy studies of the heaviest elements, and in particular enable the study of the $K^{\pi=8-}$ isomer to reveal its nucleon configuration.

The RADRIS gas cell with glowing filament in the center which is used to catch incoming recoil ions. Four lasers guided to the experiment via optical fibers and the shown output-couplers were scanned simultaneously to find one of the hidden resonances in the heaviest actinide lawrencium. Photo: Gabi Otto/GSI.

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The local team at GSI during the preparation of the RADRIS run 2022

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LASER IONISATION AND SPECTROSCOPY OF ACTINIDES

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